

Perception of medical students in Bulgaria towards abortion

Elitsa H. Gyokova^{1,2}, Ahamed Akkeel Anzaar³

¹ Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Faculty of Medicine, Medical University – Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

² University Hospital “Saint Marina” – Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

³ Medical University – Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Elitsa H. Gyokova (egyokova@yahoo.com)

Summary

Introduction: Abortion is the termination of pregnancy, whether spontaneous or intentional. Attitude regarding abortion varies widely according to culture or religion and even political siding. Restricted access to abortion leaves women in need vulnerable to seeking unsafe termination methods. **Objectives:** To gauge medical students' attitude regarding abortion and their willingness to carry out terminations as qualified doctors, and to establish factors that impacted their attitude towards it. A secondary aim was to assess students' knowledge of Bulgarian abortion laws. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted in the form of a self-administered questionnaire, which was then distributed and collected online. It consisted of five distinct sections: (A) sociodemographic data; (B) personal experience of abortion; (C) attitude; (D) knowledge of Bulgarian laws regarding abortion; and (E) willingness to perform abortions as qualified doctors. **Results:** Being Christian or Agnostic/Atheist, being in clinical years, and believing that life begins at birth showed a higher positive attitude toward abortion. On the converse, being in preclinical years, being religious, and believing that life begins at the time of conception lends itself to having a poorer attitude towards abortion. Individuals with negative attitudes denied performing abortions if the need arose during their professional careers. **Conclusion:** By appreciating the differences and understanding the relationships with attitudes towards abortion, we can create strategies to minimize the stigmatization of women and reduce the harm they may encounter with unsafe abortions.

Key words: Abortion, medical education, medical students, pregnancy termination, university curriculum

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Introduction

Abortion is the termination of pregnancy before 20 weeks of gestation, whether it occurs with medications, surgical procedures, or spontaneously.

Due to a variety of factors, the perception of abortion varies among several countries or even within the same region (Şenol and Ercoşkun 2023). Several cultures and religions around the world forbid or place restrictions on abortion, which can force women living under these laws to experience social stigmatization or overt physical harm. As a result, pregnant women under these circumstances are more inclined to seek unsafe abortions to terminate their pregnancies.

An abortion is considered safe if it is done with a method recommended by the World Health Organization and appropriate to the pregnancy duration, and if the person providing or supporting the abortion is trained. If either of these conditions is not met, the act of abortion is categorized as unsafe (Doctors Without Borders). A government decree from February 1968 was enacted to combat falling birth rates in Bulgaria by severely restricting abortions. Approval by a special medical board was required to perform most abortions, and they were generally banned for childless women with very strict medical exceptions. Despite the restrictions, abortion rates remained very high, with more abortions than live births every year between 1976 and 1990 (Johnson 2025). Since February 1990, women in Bulgaria have been able to request abortion care during the first 12 weeks of pregnancy for personal reasons. Between 12 and 20 weeks, abortion is legal only if there is a documented threat to the mother or the fetus. After 20 weeks, abortion is permitted only if the woman's life is in danger or if there is evidence of severe fetal impairment (Division 2001). According to recent studies of the Bulgarian population, there has been a significant increase in the ideal number of children in a family, with nearly 80% of couples deciding the exact number of kids to have (Hristova et al. 2018).

With the changes to laws in America and the overturning of *Roe v. Wade*, 410 U.S. 113 (Justia Law 1973), abortion is no longer conferred as a right within the United States. It was a landmark decision by the Supreme Court, which raised immediate doubts about women's right to bodily autonomy and stripped them of their decision-making power. Many physicians doubted the legality of performing abortive procedures, and it resulted in many female patients suffering due to a lack of medical care. It is now more important than ever to know about the attitude of medical students toward highly divisive topics such as abortion.

Adequate knowledge and improved attitudes among healthcare providers can reduce obstacles to safe abortion by reducing stigma and reluctance to provide abortion. According to previous studies, medical students' attitudes can predict whether they will perform abortions as qualified doctors (Aiyer et al. 1999).

Objectives

To the best of our knowledge, no studies have been conducted in Bulgaria on the attitudes of medical students towards abortion. Our goals were to determine the attitude of medical students regarding abortion and whether the views were significantly influenced by their gender, year of study, relationship status, and religious affiliation. A secondary aim was to assess medical students' knowledge regarding abortion laws in Bulgaria and their willingness to perform abortions as qualified doctors.

Methods

This is a cross-sectional study conducted using a self-administered questionnaire that was distributed online to international medical students of all years at the Medical University Pleven in Bulgaria. The questionnaire was designed in English by reviewing the previous studies (Sjöström et al. 2014; Matthews et al. 2020). The study was conducted from September 2024 to November 2024. The questionnaire included a preface that explained the purpose of the study

and a statement that ensured the optionality, anonymity, and confidentiality of the study. The questionnaire consisted of five sections: (A) sociodemographic data; (B) personal experience of abortion; (C) attitude; (D) knowledge of Bulgarian laws regarding abortion; and (E) willingness to perform abortions as qualified doctors. Descriptive and analytical statistics were used to interpret the study instrument. The data were analyzed utilizing a statistical software program for social sciences (SPSS, version 10.0).

Results

The survey was completed by 120 international medical students. Table 1 provides a summary of the participants' characteristics. Approximately 67% of the participants were female. The majority of the participants were in the age range of 18–24 years (mean age 23.3, SD 1.35), and the majority identified as being single (64.4%), with only 5.9% being married. Islam (32.5%) was the second most practiced religion after Christianity (35.8%), and 37% of participants considered themselves to be religious. About 52% of participants claimed that

Table 1. Characteristics of participants.

Characteristics	Number (%)	
Gender	Females	80 (67.2)
	Males	37 (30.8)
Country of origin	United Kingdom	33 (27.5)
	Germany	13 (10.8)
	Italy	27 (22.5)
	India	20 (16.7)
	Other	27 (22.5)
Relationship status	Single	76 (64.4)
	Domestic relationship	35 (29.7)
	Married	7 (5.9)
Religion	Islam	39 (32.5)
	Christianity	43 (35.8)
	Hinduism	12 (10)
	agnostic/atheist	22 (18.3)
	Other	4 (3.3)
Do you consider yourself to be religious?	Yes	44 (37)
	Sometimes	43 (36.1)
	Rarely	13 (10.9)
	Never	19 (16)
Do you think your religious or cultural beliefs influence your opinions regarding abortion?	Yes	32 (26.7)
	Maybe	26 (21.7)
	No	62 (51.7)
Year of study (in the medical university)	1	14 (11.8)
	2	14 (11.8)
	3	22 (18.5)
	4	16 (13.4)
	5	16 (13.4)
	6	37 (31.1)
Have you or anyone close to you had an abortion?	Yes	67 (57.8)
	No	49 (42.2)

their religious and/or cultural beliefs did not have an impact on their opinions regarding abortion. Considering the year of study, the majority of the students were in their sixth year (31.1%). More than half the students (57.8%) reported no personal exposure to or knowing someone who has had an abortion.

Medical students at Medical University Pleven begin their mandatory clinical rotation in Obstetrics and Gynecology in Year 3 and 4 of their medical degree; therefore, only responses from students in clinical years (Years 4, 5, and 6) were considered to assess the level of training in abortion care. Most of the respondents reported limited training or exposure to abortion care ($p < 0.001$). With just 8% of students engaging in abortion care, it typically consisted of the care of an adult who went through an abortion. Over half of the students claimed that the university's curriculum falls short in its coverage of abortion care. Many denied having any experience with cases of miscarriage, taking part in counseling on abortion, post-abortion complications, or the care of a minor who had an abortion (79.8%, $p < 0.001$).

To evaluate views towards abortion, students were presented with nine various reasons a woman may pursue an abortion (Table 2).

Table 2. Medical students' attitudes towards abortion.

In which of the following situations do you think abortion should be allowed?	Agreed (percentage)
In all cases	30.8%
If the pregnancy is due to incest and/ or rape	59.2%
If the woman is a minor	46.7%
If there is a threat to maternal physical and/ or mental health	60.8%
If the fetus has malformations	46.7%
If pregnancy can cause disruption of career and/ or educational goals	25%
If the pregnancy is unplanned and/ or unwanted	31.7%
If the parents wish for different gender of the fetus	3.3%
If there is financial distress	27.5%
Abortion should never be allowed	5%

Overall, the attitude of medical students towards abortion was fairly positive. 60.8% of participants reported that abortion should be allowed if there is a threat to maternal physical and/or mental health; 59.2% if the pregnancy is due to rape and/or incest; 46.6% if the woman is a minor; 46.6% if the fetus has malformations; 5% of medical students reported that abortion should not be allowed under any circumstances ($p < 0.001$). The majority of the participants agreed that the mother (95.8%) should have the authority to decide whether or not to have an abortion, but a significant number of students believed that the father (39.2%) and the healthcare provider (31.7%) should be involved in the decision as well. 39.3% of the participants agreed that life begins when the fetus has a heartbeat, whereas 25% reported that the fetus is alive at the time of delivery.

Medical students' knowledge of abortion law in Bulgaria was limited. The majority of the participants (62.5%), of whom 29.1% were in clinical years and 33.3% were in preclinical years, were unaware of the current laws in the country. About 32% of the respondents accurately identified one of the indications

of abortion, which includes termination for personal reasons within the first 12 weeks of gestation. Medical students who were in their clinical years better identified the indications for abortion, i.e., fetal malformations (14.1%), threats to maternal physical and/or mental health (18.3%), and pregnancy due to incest and/or rape (15%).

A vast majority of the participants (44.2%) were willing to perform abortions if they were legal in the country, and 35% stated that their decision to perform an abortion depends on the case. Approximately 21% of participants stated they would never perform an abortion due to their beliefs. Significant correlations existed between individuals' scores on the behavior and belief indices ($r = 0.48$, $n = 117$, $p < 0.01$), demonstrating coherence between students' predictions of their behavior in providing abortion services and their private opinions on abortion and abortion legislation.

Discussion

The attitudes of male and female participants did not differ significantly, which is consistent with the views in many European countries and the United States (Geiger 2024).

We found that being unmarried, being a clinical year medical student, being Christian or Agnostic/Atheist, and believing that life begins at the time of delivery were all characteristics associated with a positive attitude toward abortion. In contrast, being a preclinical medical student, being more religious, and believing that life begins at the time of conception were all associated with a more negative attitude. These findings were consistent with a similar study carried out in the United Kingdom (Gleeson et al. 2008).

Being female, being in a domestic partnership, being a clinical year medical student, being Christian, Agnostic/Atheist, not being religious, having had an abortion or knowing someone who had an abortion, and believing that life begins at the time of delivery are all characteristics associated with willingness to perform an abortion. Participants who rejected performing abortions as qualified doctors reported being already married, Muslim, religious, in their preclinical years, and believing that life begins at conception.

Our findings of associations between religious affiliation or religiosity and abortion views were similar to those reported among medical students in South Africa (Wheeler et al. 2012). A strong association between religious affiliation and abortion attitudes among healthcare professionals and medical students is well documented in the literature (Gleeson et al. 2008). According to some studies, physicians believe that personal religious beliefs would not prevent them from providing legal services to pregnant women, including abortion counseling, referrals, and the provision of surgical and/or medical abortion (Shotorbani et al. 2004).

According to our study, very few medical students were aware of the Bulgarian laws around abortion, and only 8% of students in their clinical years were exposed to training in abortion care. We would recommend that medical universities within the region modify their curricula to help medical students understand the legal and ethical aspect of abortion and also improve practical training in abortion care. This may increase the number of abortion providers in the future and thus limit unsafe abortions.

A major limitation of this study was the small sample size. This makes interpreting results more complicated, as it's hard to point out whether the correlations are true or only apparent within the specific sample. This could be a possible source of under-coverage bias. For future studies, we recommend distributing the questionnaire to other medical universities in Bulgaria, which would increase the sample size and lead to a more reliable reflection of the attitude of international medical students regarding abortion in Bulgaria.

By conducting similar studies amongst medical students in different geographical locations, researchers may be able to predict which regions or communities pose a higher risk to women needing abortions. Since unsafe abortions are more common in societies that hold negative attitudes, an increase in overall maternal mortality and morbidity rates due to unsafe abortions is expected (Shapiro 2013). Further investigations could be done to implement an effective method to improve the factors that negatively influence abortion attitudes.

Conclusion

With this study, we can appreciate the differences in attitudes of the participants and the factors which may have shaped them. The results help us understand the relationships between specific socioeconomic groups and their attitudes towards abortion, which can be used to devise strategies to change the public's opinion, whether that includes modifying a university's curriculum or conducting awareness campaigns directed towards the general public, but more importantly, towards medical students and health care professionals who are in direct contact with pregnant women, able to detect unsafe abortions, and capable of educating women and the general public on the Bulgarian laws and regulations that govern abortion to correct any misconceptions on this topic.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: EHG. Data curation: AAA, EHG. Formal analysis: AAA, EHG. Methodology: EHG. Writing – original draft: AAA. Writing – review and editing: EHG.

Author ORCIDs

Elitsa H. Gyokova <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4007-7961>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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